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ABSTRACTS

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Identification and characterization of endophytic fungi from *Gloriosa superba* for pharmaceutical application

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Abstract: *Gloriosa superba* stands as a significant crop with immense medicinal and industrial importance, widely utilized across traditional and modern medicinal practices. Various parts of this plant, notably its tubers, and seeds, harbor a plethora of valuable phytochemicals, prominently featuring alkaloids such as colchicine, colchicoside, and gloriosine. This species naturally thrives in regions spanning Africa, India, and Southeast Asia, having proliferated extensively throughout tropical zones. While cherished as an ornamental in temperate climates through cultivation in conservatories and greenhouses, it spans multiple regions within India.

Colchicine, a potent alkaloid, historically derived from the autumn crocus (*Colchicum autumnale* L.), has found contemporary application in treating ailments like Gout, Familial Mediterranean fever, and Bechet's disease. *G. superba*, notably its corms, contains approximately 0.9% colchicine, with seeds holding 2-5 times more colchicine content than corms or tubers. However, the rampant exploitation of these tubers may pose a threat to biodiversity, prompting exploration into alternative sources, particularly endophytes, known for producing similar bioactive compounds as the host plant. This study focused on isolating and identifying endophytic fungi from the roots, stems, and leaves of the glory lily, specifically within the Western Ghats of Maharashtra. These endophytes not only mirror the bioactive compounds of medicinal plants but also aid in metabolite degradation, mitigating potential harm to plant and microbial biodiversity. Furthermore, their beneficial presence demonstrates the potential to sustain crop yield by countering bacterial and fungal pathogens.

Keywords: *Gloriosa superba*, Colchicine, endophytic fungi, Western Ghats

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